

The **International Journal of Innovation (IJI Journal)** comes out as a result of efforts of researchers linked to distinct nuclei and research/studying groups in Universities around the world. It is an academic publication vehicle on innovation at large. IJI Journal comes out to support scientific research and state-of-the-art knowledge, **Regional or national economic development/policies related to innovation, Regional innovation strategies.**

The journal adopts a rather multifaceted approach to the many challenges facing innovation than a narrow or single target on related areas. The journal is international in character and welcomes contributions to the knowledge on innovation with international scope in **Emerging Economies** as well. It is an open, peer-blinded reviewed research-based journal, abiding by the best editorial practices and norms.

For authors, we also recommend to look at the **Editorial Policies** of this Journal. To submit your paper (**English, Portuguese and Spanish language**), please visit the online submission page (login and download template). All articles are subject to a double-blind review process. **IJI Journal** require a Contributor ID (see **ORCID and Redalyc ID**) for all authors. ORCID is a persistent unique identifier for researchers and functions similarly to an article's Digital Object Identifier (DOI). ORCIDs enable accurate attribution and improved discoverability of an author's published work. The author will need a registered ORCID in order to submit a manuscript or review a proof in this journal.

The **IJI Journal** is already indexed in: Red de Revistas Científicas de América Latina y el Caribe, España y Portugal (Redalyc); Web of Science Core Collection (Emerging Sources Citation Index), Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Ebsco Host, Portal de Portales Latindex, PKP Index, OpeinAire, Gale Cengage Learning, Proquest, Erih Plus, Dialnet and Red Iberoamericana de Innovación y Conocimiento Científico (Please, look at index sources).

Mission

Disseminate intellectual production of technological, organizational and marketing studies in the innovation field by stimulating creative contributions in unpublished academic research.

Objectives

- to contribute to increasing the knowledge from academic and professional communities in the innovation field.
- to serve as a proper channel to disseminate advances, concepts, methodologies and the experience of innovation in modern society.
- to stimulate the dissemination of knowledge that promotes new theoretical and empirical studies in the innovation field.

Focus

IJI Journal focuses on the publication of scientific contributions in the innovation field, with the preferential theme of the process of innovation in technological. Besides its regular issue, **IJI** publishes a special issue focusing on the results of research projects or relevant themes.

Target Audience

The **IJI Journal** is dedicated to a broad audience of researchers, teachers, students, entrepreneurs, consultants and other highly qualified professionals working in the innovation field in public, private and third sector organizations.

The guiding principles of **IJI Journal** target at:

- Linking scientific research on innovation and related fields to practice;
- Innovation processes, strategies, access to and supporting models and instruments to innovation;
- Intra and inter-disciplinary, multi-functional problem-oriented approach;
- Integrating innovation to business model and management.

The International Journal of Innovation accepts the following categories of articles:

1. Management of Technology and Innovation.
2. Business and International Management.
3. Strategy and Management.
4. Innovation in Emerging Economies.

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1. Innovation.
2. Entrepreneurship and Innovation
3. Management of Technology and Innovation
4. Business Innovation and Business Internationalization via Innovation
5. Innovation Strategies and Innovation Management.
6. Innovation in Emerging Economies – Frugal Innovation

The coverage includes the following specific areas:

- Government policies and regulation in innovation
- Entrepreneurship and Innovation
- Entrepreneurship and Technological and Economic Development
- Process and product innovation and diffusion
- Innovation Economy
- Innovation Marketing
- Corporate Strategies in Technology and Innovation
- Managing and commercializing intellectual property
- Management and commercialization of Innovation
- Cross-cultural management of technology and innovation
- Managing creativity and creative teams
- Innovation Environment
- Management of Technology and Innovation Change

articles

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